

EVALUATION OF FACESHEET-CORE DELAMINATION

Weiqiao Wang and Julio F. Davalos

Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering

West Virginia University

Morgantown, WV26506-6103, USA

ABSTRACT: In this paper, a linear-exponential form of the cohesive zone model (CZM) is proposed and implemented into a finite element code as a special 3D interface element, in order to simulate the facesheet/core interface delamination propagation for Honeycomb Fiber-Reinforced Polymer (HFRP) sandwich panels under mixed-mode situations. The model allows one to simulate mixed-mode delamination in a more realistic way without any preset assumptions on the mode ratio. Applying this interface element, pure mode II and mixed-mode delamination analyses of a beam specimen were successfully performed and good comparisons with closed-form solutions were obtained. A peeling delamination of an HFRP sandwich panel was also modeled, for which the global behaviors of the specimen were correctly represented based on previous similar tests.

KEYWORDS: Cohesive zone model, mixed-mode, delamination, FRP, sandwich panel.

1. INTRODUCTION

Honeycomb sandwich structures are broadly used in the aerospace and automotive industries, due to their advantageous high stiffness- and strength-to-weight ratios. Presently, there is a growing interest in composite materials for civil infrastructure rehabilitation. The concept of lightweight and heavy-duty honeycomb fiber-reinforced polymer (HFRP) sandwich panels, with sinusoidal core configuration in the plane extending vertically between face laminates, was developed for highway bridge decks by Kansas Structural Composites Inc. Stiffness characterizations for these panels have already been completed by Davalos *et al.* [1]

Fig.1 Configuration of sandwich panel.

HFRP panels consist of a sinusoidal honeycomb core attached to two facesheets with a polymer resin (Fig.1). It is critical that the bond between the facesheets and the core remain intact for the panel to perform its task. However, manufacturing defects or in-service loading conditions can often cause an initial debonding or delamination at the interface, and this initial debond may then lead to catastrophic delamination propagation, which can cause overall failure of the panel.

Research on debonding and delamination of facesheet for sandwich structures has received a great deal of interest. A relatively comprehensive literature review can be found in [2, 3]. Interface delamination can be dealt with using traditional fracture mechanics methods [4], e.g., the virtual crack closure (VCC), the J-integral, the virtual crack extension and the stiffness derivative method. In these techniques, interactions between structural behavior and the fracture process are decoupled, and their generalization to three dimensions are not straightforward, especially regarding the need for automatic remeshing. An alternative way, pioneered by Dugdale [5] and Barrenblatt [6], regards fracture as a gradual phenomenon in which separation takes place across a cohesive zone resisted by cohesive tractions. An appealing feature of this method is that it does not presume a particular type of constitutive response in the bulk of the material, and successive crack growth is a natural outcome of the analysis. This approach combined with the finite element method has been successfully applied to simulate crack propagation of various types of problems. Application of this cohesive zone model (CZM) to study facesheet/core interface delamination of honeycomb sandwich structures is rare. To our best knowledge, only one research of this kind was reported by Han et al. [7] in which buckling-driven delamination propagation of a hexagonal core honeycomb sandwich panel was addressed using the cohesive element method. The composite sandwich panels studied typically have relatively small cells of 3/16 in. and shallow cores, which are mainly used as airframe in commercial aircraft industries. In our case, since the use of sinusoidal core HFRP panels for highway bridge application is a fairly new concept, different failure mechanisms than for small-cell geometries are expected to occur.

The feasibility of applying the CZM for simulating delamination propagation of the HFRP panels was investigated in [3]. In the previous work, mode coupling was accounted for by introducing an effective ratio. In this paper, mixed-mode delamination is considered and the coupling effects are taken into account by using an interactive fracture criterion. Following the approach adopted by Crisfield and co-workers [4, 8-10], in the current formulation mixed-mode failure is treated in a manner that requires as input separate fracture toughness values, namely, G_{cI} , G_{cII} , and G_{cIII} .

2. OBJECTIVE AND SCOPE

In this paper, a linear-exponential form of the cohesive zone model (CZM) is proposed and implemented into a finite element code as a special 3D interface element, in order to simulate the facesheet/core interface delamination propagation for the HFRP sandwich panel under mixed-mode situations. The model allows one to simulate mixed-mode delamination in a more realistic way without any preset assumptions on the mode ratio. Applying this interface element, pure mode II and mixed-mode delamination analyses of a beam specimen are successfully performed and good comparisons with closed-form solutions are obtained. A peeling delamination of an HFRP sandwich panel is also modeled, for which the global behaviors of the specimen are correctly represented based on previous similar tests.

3. INTERFACE ELEMENTS

In this section, the computational framework of a 3D interface element given by Roy and Dodds [11] is followed. The interface element is a degenerate form of a 3D continuum element with initial zero-thickness as shown in Fig.2. This surface-like element consists of two, four-node bilinear isoparametric surfaces, with nodes 1-4 lying on the bottom face of the element, and nodes 5-8 on the top face. In the model generation process, these cohesive interface elements are embedded between the surrounding solid or shell elements, and each pair of top and bottom face nodes should be made coincident in the undeformed configuration.

Fig.2 3D eight-node interface element (Roy and Dodds [11])

The integration points of the element are located in the reference surface which can be defined as the top, middle or bottom face of the element. All geometrical operations such as the computation of the normal are carried out on the reference surface. Each node has three translational degrees of freedom. The global nodal displacement vector \mathbf{d} (24×1) for the element maybe written by partitioning the displacements into top and bottom faces,

$$\mathbf{d} = (\mathbf{u}_1^t, \mathbf{u}_1^b, \mathbf{u}_2^t, \mathbf{u}_2^b, \mathbf{u}_3^t, \mathbf{u}_3^b, \mathbf{u}_4^t, \mathbf{u}_4^b)^T \quad (1)$$

where displacement for each node $\mathbf{u}_i = (U, V, W)$, $i = 1-4$; the superscripts t and b denote the top and bottom faces of the interface, respectively. Using standard interpolation polynomials, the continuous displacement field, $\mathbf{u} = (\mathbf{u}^t, \mathbf{u}^b)^T$, on the top and bottom faces can be expressed in terms of the nodal displacements as

$$\mathbf{u}_{6 \times 1} = \mathbf{N}_{6 \times 24} \mathbf{d}_{24 \times 1} \quad (2)$$

where the matrix \mathbf{N} contains the usual bilinear interpolation polynomials expressed in parametric coordinates (ζ, η) located in the reference surface, $\mathcal{N}(\zeta, \eta) : [N_1(\zeta, \eta), N_2(\zeta, \eta), N_3(\zeta, \eta), N_4(\zeta, \eta)]$,

$$\mathbf{N} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{N} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \mathcal{N} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \mathcal{N} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \mathcal{N} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \mathcal{N} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \mathcal{N} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

The relative displacement field between the top and bottom faces can be obtained as

$$\Delta \mathbf{u}_{3 \times 1} = \mathbf{L}_{3 \times 6} \mathbf{u}_{6 \times 1} \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{L} is the operator matrix

$$\mathbf{L} = \begin{bmatrix} +1 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & +1 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & +1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

For computational purpose, $\Delta \mathbf{u}$ requires transformation from global coordinates to a local coordinate system constructed for the interface element. Let matrix $\mathbf{R}_{3 \times 3}$ define the orthogonal transformation from

the global reference frame (X, Y, Z) to the element specific, local coordinate system (s_1, s_2, n) (Fig.2), where the direction n lies normal to the surface of the element and the directions s_1 and s_2 lie in the surface. Finally, the relative displacement vector, $\mathbf{v} = (v_{s1}, v_{s2}, v_n)$, which defines the normal and shear separations across the cohesive surfaces can be derived as

$$\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{B} \mathbf{d} \quad (6)$$

where

$$\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{R} \mathbf{L} \mathbf{N} \quad (7)$$

Rates of the relative displacements $\dot{\mathbf{v}}$ and cohesive tractions $\dot{\mathbf{t}}$ may be coupled in standard form through a tangent modulus matrix, $\mathbf{D}_{3 \times 3}$, such that

$$\dot{\mathbf{t}} = \mathbf{D} \dot{\mathbf{v}} \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{t} = (t_{s1}, t_{s2}, t_n)^T$ and $D_{ij} = \partial t_i / \partial v_j$.

The principle of virtual work leads to the global internal nodal force vector as

$$\mathbf{f}_{24 \times 1} = \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{t} J_0 d\zeta d\eta \quad (9)$$

where J_0 is the usual Jacobian of the transformation between parametric (ζ, η) and Cartesian coordinates (s_1, s_2) . The element tangent stiffness matrix (24×24) can be obtained as

$$\mathbf{K}_T = \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{D} \mathbf{B} J_0 d\zeta d\eta \quad (10)$$

4. MATERIAL MODEL

The cohesive zone model (CZM) characterized by a softening traction-separation law is utilized to describe the interface element material behavior. In this section, a linear-exponential form of traction-separation law is proposed to study mixed-mode delamination failure of composite structures.

Fig. 3 Irreversible traction-separation relationships for mode I (a), modes II and III (b)

4.1 Uncoupled model

For the uncoupled model, linear-exponential relationships $t_i = t_i(\delta)$ are assumed for the cases of a single-mode delamination as shown in Fig.3. For pure mode I delamination, the traction-opening displacement relationship (Fig.3 (a)) is expressed as

$$t_1 = \begin{cases} K_1 \delta_1 & \text{if } \delta_1 \leq \delta_{c1} \\ K_1 \delta_1 e^{1-\delta_1/\delta_{c1}} & \text{if } \delta_1 > \delta_{c1} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

In (11) the penalty-like stiffness is $K_1 = \sigma_{c1} / \delta_{c1}$; σ_{c1} is the peak traction; $e = \exp(1)$ and δ_{c1} denotes the critical value of δ_1 at $t_1 = \sigma_{c1}$. Under compression $\delta_1 < 0$, and in order to avoid penetration, a relatively high stiffness is assumed.

For pure mode II or mode III problem, the traction-sliding displacement relationship is depicted in Fig. 3(b). For $\delta_2, \delta_3 > 0$, it is the same as for mode I, whereas for $\delta_2, \delta_3 < 0$ it is antisymmetric with respect to the origin. The analytical expression is

$$t_\alpha = \begin{cases} K_\alpha \delta_\alpha & \text{if } |\delta_\alpha| \leq \delta_{c\alpha} \\ K_\alpha \delta_\alpha e^{1-\delta_\alpha/\delta_{c\alpha}} & \text{if } |\delta_\alpha| > \delta_{c\alpha} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

where $K_\alpha = \sigma_{c\alpha} / \delta_{c\alpha}$; $\alpha = 2, 3$.

The irreversibility of the interface damage can be taken into account by the following relation

$$t_i = \frac{(t_i)_{\max}}{(\delta_i)_{\max}} \delta_i \quad \text{if } |\delta_i| < (\delta_i)_{\max} \text{ or } \dot{\delta}_i < 0 \quad (13)$$

where $(t_i)_{\max}$ and $(\delta_i)_{\max}$ are the maximum tractions and relative displacements throughout a loading history, $i = 1-3$. By (13), cohesive surfaces are assumed to unload to the origin.

The areas under the traction-relative displacement curves are assumed to be equal to the critical energy release rates, namely, G_{cI} , G_{cII} , G_{cIII} which are characteristic parameters of the interface and can be measured separately by single-mode delamination tests.

$$G_{ci} = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{ci} \delta_{ci} + \int_{\delta_{ci}}^{\infty} t_i d\delta_i = 2.5 \sigma_{ci} \delta_{ci} \quad (14)$$

4.2 Mixed-mode model

Following the approach in [4, 8-10], mixed-mode delamination can be extended to three-dimensional cases for the linear-exponential traction-separation law described above. A scalar $\bar{\gamma}$ which accounts for the interactions between mode I, mode II and mode III is defined as

$$\bar{\gamma}(t) = \max_{0 \leq t' \leq t} \gamma(t') \quad (15)$$

where

$$\gamma(t') = \left[\left(\frac{\langle \delta_1(t') \rangle}{\delta_{c1}} \right)^\alpha + \left(\frac{|\delta_2(t')|}{\delta_{c2}} \right)^\alpha + \left(\frac{|\delta_3(t')|}{\delta_{c3}} \right)^\alpha \right]^{1/\alpha} - 1 \quad (16)$$

with the scalar α being a material parameter, which will generally assume values between 2 and 4. For $\delta_i < 0$, since mode I should not contribute to the damage process, the Mc Cauley bracket $\langle \cdot \rangle$ is used as

$$\langle x \rangle = \begin{cases} x & \text{if } x \geq 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } x \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

Before δ_{ci} is reached, it is assumed that there are no interface damage and no coupling between different modes. The mixed-mode constitutive relationship is then given by

$$t_i = \begin{cases} K_i \delta_i & \text{if } \bar{\gamma}(t) \leq 0 \\ K_i \delta_i e^{-\bar{\gamma}} & \text{if } \bar{\gamma}(t) > 0 \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

With the above mixed-mode relationship, if a fixed mode ratio is assumed, the following general fracture criterion can be fulfilled

$$\left(\frac{G_I}{G_{cI}} \right)^{\alpha/2} + \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_{cII}} \right)^{\alpha/2} + \left(\frac{G_{III}}{G_{cIII}} \right)^{\alpha/2} = 1 \quad (19)$$

For $\alpha = 2$ and $\alpha = 4$, a linear and a quadratic interaction criterion are recovered, respectively. By differentiating (18) with respect to δ_i , the element tangent modulus can be obtained as

$$D_{ij} = \begin{cases} \delta_{ij} K_i & \text{if } \bar{\gamma}(t) \leq 0 \\ -\frac{e^{-\bar{\gamma}}}{(1 + \bar{\gamma})^{\alpha-1}} \left[K_i \delta_i \frac{\tilde{\delta}_j^{\alpha-1}}{\delta_{cj}^\alpha} - \delta_{ij} K_i (1 + \bar{\gamma})^{\alpha-1} \right] & \text{if } \bar{\gamma}(t) > 0 \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

where $i, j = 1-3$; δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta; and $\tilde{\delta}_1 = \langle \delta_1 \rangle$, $\tilde{\delta}_2 = |\delta_2|$, $\tilde{\delta}_3 = |\delta_3|$. From (20), a non-symmetric tangent stiffness matrix is produced unless $\alpha = 2$ and the same properties are used for mode I, II and III.

For unloading cases, relationship (13) still holds, and the tangent modulus is

$$D_{ij} = \delta_{ij} e^{-\bar{\gamma}} K_i \quad (21)$$

5. NUMERICAL SIMULATION

The CZM described in section 3 and 4 is implemented in the commercial finite element code ABAQUS [12] via a user-defined element subroutine UEL. In this section, applying this cohesive interface element, a mixed-mode delamination analysis is firstly performed to simulate the experimental set-up of Reeder and Crews [13]. Then a peeling delamination of an HFRP sandwich panel is also modeled in an effort to utilize this method for further investigation.

5.1 Simulation of mixed-mode testing

This specimen was also chosen by Mi *et al.* [8] for a 2D delamination simulation as illustrated in Fig.4, for which an initial crack was placed at the mid-plane. By varying the loading length c , different mode ratios can be achieved. The closed form solutions was given by Allix *et al.* [14] for modes I and II, and extended by Mi *et al.* [8] to include mixed-mode situations. The dimensions and properties for the simulations are as follows:

$$L = 50 \text{ mm}, a = 30 \text{ mm}, h = 3 \text{ mm}, B = 1 \text{ mm}$$

$$E_x = 135,300 \text{ N/mm}^2, E_y = E_z = 9,000 \text{ N/mm}^2, G_{xy} = 5,200 \text{ N/mm}^2, \nu_{xy} = \nu_{xz} = 0.24, \nu_{yz} = 0.46$$

$$G_{cI} = G_{cII} = G_{cIII} = 4.0 \text{ N/mm}, \sigma_{c1} = \sigma_{c2} = \sigma_{c3} = 57 \text{ N/mm}^2$$

where h is the height of the specimen and B is the width.

Fig.4 Mixed-Mode testing: a) experimental set-up; b) loads applied to the specimen (Mi *et al.* [8])

A 3-D finite element (FE) model is created. The model uses 750 interface elements and 1950 solid elements, with 2 elements in the beam width direction. Gap elements are used for the initial crack length to simulate contact behavior. In order to obtain a relatively smooth solution, the mesh must be fine enough in the evolving “process zone” near the crack front. In addition, relatively small displacement increments are prescribed, through an adaptive step-size reduction algorithm of the interface element, to capture important features of the “process zone,” such as peak stress.

Firstly, we will consider a pure mode II situation by setting c to zero; i.e., loading the beam at its center. Finite element analysis results are plotted against closed-form solutions in Fig.5. There are three curves associated with the analytical solutions: the linear part OB is related to a cantilever with an initial crack length a , whereas segment ABC is the unloading line from conventional energy release (G_{cII}) computations for $a < L$, and curve DE is the loading line for $a > L$. From the figure, we can observe that the FE analysis agrees well with the closed-form solutions.

The mixed-mode case is then studied setting c to 41.5 mm so that $G_I/G_{II} = 1.0$. In Fig.6, load-deflection responses at the specimen end are shown from both the FE analysis and closed-form solutions. It can be seen that different mixed-mode interaction criteria, e.g., linear or quadratic criterion, would lead to distinct structural responses. Nevertheless, it is reported that most of the experimental results lie between these two limit cases [15]. Also, the FE simulation predicts well the overall behavior of the specimen compared with closed-form solutions.

Fig.5 Load-deflection responses for mode-II beam test

Fig.6 Load-deflection responses for mixed-mode test

5.2 Peeling simulation of an HFRP sandwich panel

For applications to the mixed-mode delamination of HFRP sandwich panels, the CZM can be characterized by two parameters for each mode, i.e., the interface fracture toughness G_{ci} and the interface strength σ_{ci} . The critical displacements can then be determined from (14). For mode I, G_{cI} and σ_{cI} may be determined through the interface fracture toughness test and the flat-wise tension test, respectively, as described in [2, 3]. For modes II and III, lacking experimental data currently, G_{cII} and G_{cIII} are assumed to be 10% of G_{cI} , and the shear strengths σ_{cII} and σ_{cIII} are assumed to be 3 times of σ_{cI} .

Fig.7 FE model of peeling test of an HFRP sandwich panel

The FE model of peeling test of an HFRP sandwich panel is shown in Fig.7. For simplicity, the sandwich core for the simulation consists of five evenly spaced vertical panels instead of sinusoidal configurations. All the nonlinearities are assumed to occur within the cohesive interface elements. The facesheets and the honeycomb core are modeled as linear elastic materials. The facesheets are modeled with four-node shell elements, and the sandwich core is modeled using shell elements for the most part, while using solid elements near the interface to accommodate solid interface elements between the facesheet and the core. The initial crack length is $a = 4.4$ in. The bonding layer, i.e., the interface, between the facesheet and the core, is modeled using the eight-node interface elements. Mode I interface fracture toughness G_{cI} is determined using the actual core thickness rather than the total panel width in [2], since interface elements are placed only between the core solid elements and facesheet shell elements. The bottom side of the panel is fixed and the load tip is applied at one end under displacement control. The whole model has 549 solid elements, 4179 shell elements, and 439 interface elements.

Fig.8 Load-displacement at the load end for the peeling test

Dimensions of the panel are: $22'' \times 1.75'' \times 2''$ (length \times width \times height), core thickness = $0.06''$, facesheet thickness = $0.2022''$. Material properties are:

Core: $E_1 = E_2 = 1,710,000$ psi, $G_{12} = G_{13} = 610,609$ psi, $G_{23} = 430,762$ psi, $\nu_{12} = 0.4$;

Facesheet: $E_1 = 1,870,000$ psi, $E_2 = 1,710,000$ psi, $G_{12} = G_{13} = 530,000$ psi, $G_{23} = 38,100$ psi, $\nu_{12} = 0.4$;

Interface: $G_{cI} = 51$ lb/in., $G_{cII} = G_{cIII} = 5.1$ lb/in., $\sigma_{cI} = 750$ psi, $\sigma_{cII} = \sigma_{cIII} = 2,250$ psi.

The load vs. displacement relationship is plotted in Fig.8. No experimental data is currently available for comparison; nonetheless, the progressive delamination process is successfully simulated, and the global trend of the structural responses is reasonable compared to a DCB specimen tested previously [2].

6. CONCLUSIONS

It is concluded from this initial work that the proposed linear-exponential CZM shows great potential for simulating facesheet/core interface delamination propagation of HFRP sandwich panels. An extensive experimental program is underway for application of this approach to various actual cases.

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